

**ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL
ERRORS DURING THE USE OF
ENGLISH BY ALBANIAN STUDENTS:
CAUSES AND IMPROVEMENTS
(CORRECTIONS)**

Morphology

Keywords: Grammatical errors, mistakes, performance errors, competence errors, etc.

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Abstract

Albanian students have many difficulties when using English as the second/foreign language in the classroom. This study will be based on second language learning research (English) and only on speaking errors made from the 12th grade students of Secondary High School “Xhelal Hajda – Toni” in Rahovec, in terms of the most common mistakes. The main focus of the study is the elaboration of facts in: 1. mistakes students make when speaking; 2. Grammatical errors when learning English in the classroom environment; 3. To what extent the oral corrective reaction emotionally affects students learning English and how they react and respond to the spoken feedback process; 4. What is the role of correcting these grammatical errors in teaching, as well as how teachers will need to approach these errors when making them in the classroom environment; 5. Introducing techniques that can be used to control mistakes when speaking to students, a procedure that enables them to become more aware of the type of mistake they have made and thus how can they correct these mistakes by themselves.

Purpose of the Study

The main focus of the study consists a) mainly on speaking errors and the most common mistakes that are caused among students in classroom; b) The second goal is to find the causes of the errors and how they can be corrected; c) The third goal is to investigate the way teachers give their corrective feedback regarding the correction of these errors and how they motivate students with their attitudes in the classroom.

Main Objectives

The main objective of the study is to collect, categorize, systematize, analyze and clarify the mistakes that students make in speaking.

Research Questions

1. Do Albanian students who learn a foreign language (in our case English) face difficulties in terms of grammatical errors?
2. How interested are Albanian teachers with finding speech errors made by their students learning English as a foreign language in terms of grammatical errors and their analysis?
3. Does making grammatical mistakes affect learning English as a foreign language?
4. Does the teacher play an important role in finding, explaining and correcting these types of mistakes?

5. How much does the teacher influence the investigation and corrective reaction of these types of mistakes during the student teaching process?
6. How difficult is it for Albanian students to learn English, what are the possible causes of grammatical errors and how are they classified?

Hypotheses

1. Acquisition, competence and frequency of morphological errors encountered in communication of English as a foreign / second language by 12th grade students at the High School “Xhelal Hajda – Toni” in Rahovec area is at an unsatisfactory level and;
2. One of the main factors during the analysis of morphological errors in the use of English as a foreign / second language by the same students is the intervention / interference and simplification used by students from their native language to English.

Importance of the Study

Lack of research papers related to the analysis of morphological errors in the use of English as a foreign language to clearly explain the connection of morphology and its impact on other branches of linguistics. Identifying the influencing factors and causes for these morphological errors, discussing, analyzing and providing recommendations or suggestions about their improvement or correction is of special contribution.

Target Results

The expected results from this research study are: 1. Information; 2. Analysis; and 3. Awareness. Regarding the analysis of morphological errors during the use of English by Albanian students: causes and improvements. Listing the main factors of these morphological errors, analysis and motivation in avoiding these errors.

Literature Review

The use of English is almost inevitable, especially in the fields of doing business, education, employment, media, etc. According to Rashid et al., (2017), mastering the English language in different countries has become more a necessity for an individual than an opportunity to learn. The study by Dulay and Burt (1975) proposes that a second language develop during childhood.

Morphemes, Their Study and Classification

Todd (1987) states that morphology is the study of morphemes. Morphemes are of two types:

1. Free morphemes; and 2. Bound morphemes.

Types of Morphological Errors

Researchers in the field of applied linguistics usually identify two main types of errors:

1. Performance Errors; and 2. Competence Errors. Other scholars such as Burt and Kiparsky (1974) classify errors as follows: 1. Local errors; and 2. Global errors.

The Main Causes of Morphological Errors

1. Simplification of complex morphological forms,
2. Excessive generalization of morphological forms,
3. Hypercorrection,
4. Wrong teaching,
5. Fossilization,
6. Avoidance,
7. Inadequate learning,
8. Hypothetical false concepts.
9. Proper treatment and correction of morphological errors by teachers.

Useful Teaching Strategies and Methods in Correct Morphology Learning

1. Teachers need to put more emphasis on correcting mistakes, 2. Teachers need to put more emphasis on the pedagogical focus, 3. Tips for correcting mistakes, 4. Focus on the message that the students are communicating, 5. Find the right time, 6. Use mistakes as examples, 7. Focus on improvements, 9. Use suggestive tools, 10. Individual conversation, 11. Peer review and editing.

Study Methodology

Several methodologies have been used to work on this study. Initially, questionnaires or surveyors were used as a tool for qualitative research. Participants in this study were students attending classes in the 12th grade at the High School “Xhelal Hajda – Toni” in the municipality of Rahovec, (with a total of one hundred participants (100), and eight teachers (8) of English language in the same school).

Study Instruments

In this research the mix method was used – Quantitative and Qualitative. A questionnaire was designed for participating students, this questionnaire mainly contained questions about students' attitudes towards morphological errors; With this questionnaire we analyzed the role of the teacher and the inclusion of contemporary methodologies in correcting morphological errors when using the English language. It was then designed for participating teachers, through which some of the useful teaching strategies and methods were researched which according to the participating teachers are useful in avoiding morphological errors and in learning the correct morphology.

Results

I found it more reasonable to present the results in tables based on the percentage of answers of the students in the questionnaire. In tables are given questions and the result in the percentage.

1. Which of the following components is the primary component that boosts your motivation?

2. The most common morphological errors when speaking English

3. Characteristics of morphological errors in English language learning

4. Which is the most effective option in correcting morphological errors?

5. What are the main factors in encountering morphological difficulties and errors in English?

6. Qualities and strategies of motivating teachers

7. The teacher promotes the success of the school and its students

Useful Teaching Strategies in Correct Morphology Learning

A total of eleven (11) contemporary strategies and methods were listed, and teachers had the opportunity to list the options based on their exercise and preference. All these strategies are in line with modern curricula and are considered the most useful methods in avoiding morphological errors.

Conclusion and Recommendation

As a conclusion, this study provides the following recommendations based on the results obtained: all teachers and experts in the field of English language teaching are recommended to provide additional lectures and free trainings, to keep additional information, to organize various workshops, meetings, morphological exercises and seminars with students, teachers and English language colleagues, to provide more discussion in general, ease of exercises, practice of more complex exercises, and combinations of exercises so that students are in principle well informed

about the dangers and consequences of morphological errors as important errors in language acquisition.

Advices to the Teachers for Correcting Mistakes

1. Focus on the message that students are communicating,
2. Find the right time;
3. Use mistakes as examples;
4. Focus on improvements;
5. Use suggestive tools;
6. Individual conversation;
7. Peer review and editing.

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